

On the Polarographic Reduction Mechanism of Some Heterocyclic Compounds

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For evaluating the mechanistic steps, position at d.m.e and assigning inner or outer sphere path of electrode processes of a number of pyrazole derivatives, thiazoles and their precursors experiments were carried out in the absence and presence of surfactants. All the compounds gave diffusion-controlled, irreversible waves over the entire pH range (2.0-11.0) studied. In presence of surfactants also, diffusion-controlled but more irreversible waves were obtained. In absence and presence of surfactant (CTAB) values of K_{app} and α_{app} for all these compounds were calculated and have been taken as a proof of inner sphere or outer sphere path of the electrode reaction. Results have been explained on the basis of formation of phenylazo-function-alised surfactant as an intermediate species.

THE electrochemical reaction at an electrode may either take place in the close vicinity of the electrode or a little far off from the electrode surface. In physico-chemical terminology the former are named as reactions in the 'Inner Helmholtz Plane' (IHP) and the latter as reactions in the 'Outer Helmholtz Plane' (OHP). Generally speaking substances which are easily reducible get reduced in the OHP while difficultly reducible species are reduced in the IHP.

Anson and co-workers^{1,2} for the first time attempted to distinguish between IHP and OHP reduction paths in the case of Cr(III) cyanogen complexes. According to them since inorganic ions are easily hydrated or solvated they do not get adsorbed at the electrode and, therefore, undergo reduction easily. On the other hand complexes such as dichromium complexes, which show fair tendency to adsorb, do so by inner sphere path. This distinction can be very well evaluated by carrying out reduction studies in the presence of strongly adsorbable substances.

Literature survey revealed that such studies have not been undertaken with organic compounds. A large majority of compounds, unless they have got a strong lyophilic end group, are adsorbed at the electrode surface and would very likely, show IHP reduction path.

Recently we have reported³⁻⁵ the polarographic reduction of a number of heterocyclic compounds without evaluating the mechanistic steps and their respective position at the d.m.e. Moreover assigning inner or outer sphere path to a variety of compounds would also help in explaining the comparative ease of reduction in various series of compounds.

Keeping in view the importance of the various parameters for distinguishing the two types of mechanistic path, we have considered the following series of compounds :

- (i) Coupled products of aryldiazonium chlorides with β -ketoesters, which are precursors of various biologically important compounds.
- (ii) 2-Benzothiazolyldrazono ethyl-2-cyanoethanoates.
- (iii) 4-Arylhydrazono - N'-phenylthiocarbamoyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-ones.
- (iv) N'-Phenylthiocarbamoyl-3,5-dimethyl-4-arylazopyrazoles, and
- (v) N'-Phenyl-3,5-dimethyl-4-arylazopyrazoles.

Further confirmation in this respect has been made available by considering corresponding data in the presence of surfactants.

Experimental

Five series of compounds including precursors of various heterocycles, coupled products of aryldiazonium chlorides with β -ketoesters, hydrazono compounds (viz., 2-benzothiazolyldrazono, 2-cyanoethanoates, pyrazolin-5-ones) and azo compounds (phenylazothiocarbamoylpyrazoles, phenylazopyrazoles) were synthesised by literature methods⁶⁻¹². All the compounds were recrystallised from ethanol and their structural characteristics were confirmed by chemical and spectral analysis.

The stock solutions of concentration $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ of all the compounds were prepared in methanol. Britton-Robinson buffer in the pH range 2.0 to 11.0 and 1.0 M KCl, 0.01 M cetyltrimethylammonium

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bromide (CTAB) was prepared in doubly distilled water. All the chemicals and solvents used were of A.R. grade. Solutions for polarographic measurements were prepared by mixing 1.0 ml of the compound, 2.0 ml of methanol, 1.0 ml of 1.0 M KCl and 6.0 ml of the B.R. buffer. Polarograms were then recorded by adding CTAB 0.1 ml to 1.0 ml of each case. Dissolved oxygen was removed from the solution by passing purified hydrogen gas for about 10 min.

Apparatus: Polarographic curves were recorded on a Cambridge pen recording polarograph. The capillary characteristic was $2.07 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ S}^{1/2}$ at a zero potential in 1.0 M KCl solution. The temperature of the solution was maintained at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ by keeping the polarographic cell in a thermostatic bath. The pH metric measurements were made on the Expanded Scale L1 10 pH meter with glass electrodes. SCE was used as the reference electrode.

Results and Discussion

All the compounds gave diffusion controlled, irreversible wave over the entire pH range (2.0-11.0) studied. The half-wave potential was pH dependent whereas the limiting current was pH independent. Afterwards, polarograms were recorded in presence of different amounts of CTAB (0.1-1.0 ml). In presence of surfactant also, diffusion controlled but more irreversible (Tables 1-5) waves were obtained. $E_{1/2}$ of these waves were also pH dependent and the i_a remained pH independent.

TABLE 3—VALUES OF K_{app} LOG AND α_{app} FOR ELECTRO REDUCTION OF 4-ARYLAZODRAZONO-N-PHENYLTHIO CARBAMOYL-3-METHYL-2-PYRAZOLIN-5-ONES AT pH 6.0

R	$-\log K_{app} \text{ (cm}^{-1}\text{)}$		α_{app}	
	(a)*	(b)*	(a)*	(b)*
H	0.31	0.33	0.12	0.09
2-CH ₃	0.39	0.40	0.10	0.06
2-OCH ₃	0.36	0.41	0.14	0.11

* (a) In the absence of surfactant.
(b) In the presence of surfactant.

TABLE 4—VALUES OF $-\log K_{app}$ AND α_{app} FOR ELECTRO REDUCTION OF N'-PHENYLTHIOCARBAMOYL-3,5-DIMETHYL-4-ARYLAZOPYRAZOLES AT pH 6.0

R	$-\log K_{app} \text{ (cm}^{-1}\text{)}$		α_{app}	
	(a)*	(b)*	(a)*	(b)*
H	0.15	0.20	0.37	0.34
2-OCH ₃	0.19	0.22	0.39	0.35
3-OCH ₃	0.15	0.22	0.40	0.38

* (a) In the absence of surfactant.
(b) In the presence of surfactant.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF $-\log K_{app}$ AND α_{app} FOR ELECTRO REDUCTION OF COUPLED PRODUCTS OF ARYLDIAZONIUM CHLORIDES WITH β -KETOESTER AT pH 6.0

R	$-\log K_{app} \text{ (cm}^{-1}\text{)}$		α_{app}	
	(a)*	(b)*	(a)*	(b)*
H	0.37	0.40	0.21	0.17
2-CH ₃	0.30	0.35	0.25	0.22
3-CH ₃	0.32	0.35	0.22	0.18
4-CH ₃	0.37	0.41	0.22	0.19
2-Cl	0.25	0.32	0.21	0.16
3-Cl	0.32	0.35	0.27	0.21
4-Cl	0.32	0.36	0.22	0.18

* (a) In the absence of surfactant.
(b) In the presence of surfactant.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF $-\log K_{app}$ AND α_{app} FOR ELECTRO REDUCTION OF 2-BENZOTHAZOLYLHYDRAZONO ETHYL-2-CYANOETHANOATES AT pH 6.0

R	$-\log K_{app} \text{ (cm}^{-1}\text{)}$		α_{app}	
	(a)*	(b)*	(a)*	(b)*
H	0.28	0.30	0.14	0.10
2-CH ₃	0.31	0.35	0.10	0.07
4-CH ₃	0.27	0.31	0.12	0.08

* (a) In the absence of surfactant.
(b) In the presence of surfactant.

TABLE 5—VALUES OF $-\log K_{app}$ AND α_{app} FOR ELECTRO REDUCTION OF N'-PHENYL-3,5-DIMETHYL-4-ARYLAZOPYRAZOLES AT pH 6.0

R	$-\log K_{app} \text{ (cm}^{-1}\text{)}$		α_{app}	
	(a)*	(b)*	(a)*	(b)*
H	0.23	0.28	0.32	0.30
2-CH ₃	0.20	0.24	0.35	0.28
3-CH ₃	0.21	0.24	0.32	0.31
4-CH ₃	0.20	0.25	0.34	0.32
2-Cl	0.25	0.28	0.37	0.31
3-Cl	0.23	0.27	0.35	0.31
4-Cl	0.20	0.26	0.39	0.33

* (a) In the absence of surfactant.
(b) In the presence of surfactant.

Rate of reduction (K_{app}) for both inner and outer sphere reduction at the mercury electrode surface is given by the equation,

$$\log K_{app} = \log \frac{i}{Fc_b}$$

where i is the current density at the rising part of the waves at a potential $-E$, C_b the bulk concentration of the depolarizer and K_{app} the rate constant

for reduction. In presence and absence of CTAB, values of K_{app} for all these compounds were calculated and are given in Tables 1-5. The above equation can be used successfully to differentiate between the two paths by monitoring the changes in the K_{app} in absence and presence of surfactants. If surfactant causes some change in the values of K_{app} it may be taken as a proof of inner sphere path otherwise it indicates outer sphere path.

It may be further observed that for a particular solution of constant concentration of the depolarizer and the supporting electrolyte, the plot of $\log K_{app}$ (determined at various potentials $-E$, on the rising part of the wave) against $-E$ should be linear and is given by the equation :

$$\frac{\partial \log K_{app}}{\partial E} = \frac{\alpha}{2.303 RT} \left(\frac{\partial \Delta G_{AP}^{\circ}}{\partial E} + F \right) - \frac{1-\alpha_1}{2.303} RT \left(\frac{\partial \Delta G_{AR}^{\circ}}{\partial E} \right)$$

Since the magnitude and sign of the free energy terms will significantly vary for an inner- and outer-sphere path, the value of α_{app} will also vary. The α_{app} values thus can be utilised to differentiate between the two paths. The values of α_{app} has been evaluated from the slopes of plots (Tafel P lots) of $\log K_{app}$ against $-E$, which gives

$$\alpha_{app} = - \frac{2.303 RT}{F} \left(\frac{\partial \log K_{app}}{\partial E} \right)$$

when values of α_{app} are above 0.5, the electrode process is assumed to be taking in outer sphere whereas values lower than 0.5 indicates inner sphere path. Hence it is obvious that values of K_{app} and α_{app} for a particular compound may be utilised to distinguish between the inner and outer sphere path of the electrode reactions. α_{app} values for five series of compounds in presence and absence of surfactant are given in Tables 1-5.

On reviewing the data in Tables 1-5 some interesting trend in the values of K_{app} and α_{app} for these five series of compounds was observed. For azo compounds the values of K_{app} and α_{app} are higher than for hydrazono compounds. But for both type of compound viz., azo and hydrazono, K_{app} and α_{app} decreases in presence of surfactant indicating that reduction is taking place at the inner sphere of the electrode. Moreover, the values of α_{app} for azo and hydrazono compounds are below 0.5, and further point towards the inner sphere mechanism of the electrode process.

On the basis of values of K_{app} and α_{app} it appears possible to categorise azo and hydrazono compounds. Interestingly, compounds having azo group reduce at more positive potential ($E_{1/2} = 0.2$ to 0.6 , at pH 6.0) than compounds with hydrazono

group ($E_{1/2} = 0.5$ to 0.8 at pH 6.0), indicating the easy reduction of azo group to hydrazono group. Higher values of K_{app} and α_{app} in case of azo compounds are in similar tune.

The lower rate (K_{app}) of the electrode process in the presence of cationic surfactant (CTAB) may be due to the formation of surfactant depolarizer complex. The surfactant micelles do not diffuse as such in the outer plane of the Helmholtz double layer but it is the surfactant depolarizer complex which reaches the inner part of the double layer, orients itself towards electrode surface and subsequently get reduced. The possible mechanism may be as follows (H^+ , e , e , H^+ mechanism)¹⁸ :

In this mechanism free radical (III) form surfactant-depolarizer complex with cationic surfactant (CTAB). This surfactant-depolarizer complex may diffuse to the inner part of the double layer and get reduced to (VI) after the uptake of an electron and a proton, and releasing the surfactant as such.

(2) Alternatively,

This mechanism appears to be more probable due to the easy availability of species $C_{16}H_{33}^+N(CH_3)_4$ in the solution. After the formation of phenylazo-functionalised surfactant (VII) (formed by the interaction of polarizer $-N=N-$ group) it gets protonated to give protonated species (VIII). The protonated intermediate then reduces to (XI) similarly as in the case of mechanism (1).

In the same way, effect of cationic surfactant on hydrazono compounds can be explained on the basis of more probable mechanism (2), as follows :

Here, functionalised surfactant (XII) which reaches the inner part of the double layer, get reduced to give aniline and another amine (XIV), following the steps (H^+ , e^- , e^- , H^+).

It is quite clear from the above mechanism that reduction of hydrazono group involves initial breakage of -NH-N- bond followed by uptake of

two more protons and electrons. Since more energy is required for the cleavage of -NH-N- bond, E_3 is more negative than azo compounds.

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